

***Mise-en-abyme* as narrative strategy in the films of Wes Anderson**

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Bio: Rubén de la Prida Caballero (Madrid, 1982) is a PhD Candidate in Audiovisual Communication, Publicity and PR. His dissertation topic is *The Cinema of Wes Anderson*. He graduated in Mechanical Engineering and balances his professional career as a railway consultant with research and teaching in Cinema as well as Mechanics. He holds a Master in Film Critic from the *School of Cinematography and Audiovisual of the Community of Madrid* (ECAM), and is the author of numerous articles.

Abstract: One of the central aspects of Wes Anderson's cinema, characteristic of his authorial style, is the use of the *mise-en-abyme* both as a narrative and as a stylistic resource. Starting principally with his second feature film *Rushmore* (1998), Wes Anderson has been using a number of reflective and metadiscursive strategies related to the *mise-en-abyme*, such as *tableaux vivants* conceived as theater stages, theater plays, texts such as films or books that work as framing devices of the film diegesis, extradiegetic presences, complex shots that use mirrors - or the camera lens itself as a mirror -, silhouettes, narrations within other narrations, etc. All these mechanisms make up one of the most recognizable trademarks of Anderson's disruptive use of the possibilities of the medium; accordingly his cinema refers to a sort of ubiquitous matryoshka-like aesthetics, related to the collector's quality of Anderson's cinema as defined by Donna Kornhaber (2017). The paper focuses on the *mise-en-abyme* as a fundamental, underlying narrative strategy in Wes Anderson's cinema that can be considered as a meta-sign of the enunciation, thus recognizable in many of the visual expressions of the director's unmistakable cinematic language.

Keywords: Wes Anderson; *mise-en-abyme*; enunciation; aesthetics; metadiscourse.

In 1948, Alexandre Astruc published his revolutionary manifesto *Naissance d'une nouvelle avant-garde: La caméra-stylo*. The article was both the starting point of the author theory and the first of a series of milestones in the foundation and development of the French New Wave. The central point of Astruc's propositions can be summarized in his affirmation that "[d]irection is no longer a means of illustrating or presenting a scene, but a true act of writing. The film-maker/author writes with his camera as a writer writes with his pen" (Astruc, 1948, p. 6). In narratologic terms, one could define this principle as a subsidiary to the transition from a mimetic narrative, typical of the classical era of cinema, where the story seems to tell itself, to a diegetic narrative, which evinces the fingerprints of the writer-director, that is, of the enunciator. The author's recognizable presence in his¹ film occurs via the signs of the enunciation, hallmarks that unmistakably refer to his particular aesthetics, i.e., to his own and consistent set of thematic and stylistic constants.

Interestingly enough, one of the works that has examined Wes Anderson's authorship (and authors) in a more poignant way refers to Astruc's manifesto in its very title. Devin Orgeron's seminal article *La Caméra-Crayola: Authorship Comes of Age in the Cinema of Wes Anderson* (Orgeron, 2007) underlines the position of Anderson as a contradictory renovator of the figure of the author, offering that "something new" (p. 59) to the author question that Adrian Martin (2004) claimed. Among other topics, Orgeron explains Anderson's ability to create his own authorial image, related both to the establishment of a community of collaborators as well as of a community of fans, something typical for the authors who populate his films². This creation has of course to do with a commercial strategy, as Orgeron (p. 42) points out, following Timothy Corrigan (2003), related to the emergence of the DVD technology. Dorey (2012) widens this thesis, by showing how the paratexts associated with Anderson's movies, fundamentally those included in the privileged Criterion editions of his films, help construct and sustain his particular kind of auteurism, which could be termed as Andersonianism. Certainly, many of these paratexts - which include audio commentaries of the films, making-of's, as well as reviews and analyses - are undoubtedly a new, extracinematic explanation of the director's authorship. Yet, these paratexts, however helpful they may be when constructing Anderson's authorial persona, and in spite of explaining some of the motivations, intertexts and particularities of the Andersonian aesthetics, fail to explain the underlying strategies that relate and sustain the different expressions of Anderson's cinematic language.

Andersonianism is logically not only explained by these extracinematic materials: it also and mainly subsists within the peculiar aesthetics characteristic of the director's movies. The visual component of such aesthetics is particularly recognizable, as Anderson's fans like to underline - one might recall, for example, the volume *Accidentally Wes Anderson* (Koval, 2020) - and his critics love to discard, "generally [pointing] to the very same attributes" (Brinkema, 2021, p. 73). To date some scholars have explored Anderson's visual style; yet, in my opinion, these contributions also fail, like the paratexts, to explain how these trademarks are intrinsically linked to each other at a deep, narratological level, beyond pertaining to the peculiar style of their enunciator or some of its most superficial aspects. A good example is the extensive and fundamental analysis of Anderson's *mise-en-scène* carried out by Sunhee Lee (2016), in which the author explains some of the most striking visual characteristics of Anderson's work - long tracking shots, tableau shots, overhead close

shots, slow motion, handheld camera or recognizable props - contextualizing them within the characteristic ambivalence of the relationships between form and content, but as if they were in essence independent manifestations of style without a narrative connection to each other. On the other hand, the original contribution by Peter Sloane (2018), refers more clearly to some of the strategies listed in the present paper; however, the author does not point out their common narrative purpose, rather relating them to a particular conception of filmic space, reminiscent of the bi-dimensionality of printed books.

However, the recent monograph by Warren Buckland (2019) delves - for the first time - deeply under the surface of Anderson's work in an intent to recognize, from the perspective of semiotics and structuralism, the "underlying abstract codes that convey order, unity and meaning" (p. ix) within the whole of the Andersonian aesthetics. In an analogous manner, yet on a more modest scale and via a formalist and narratologic approach complementary to Buckland's, the present paper aims to provide the description of *one* underlying narrative strategy in Anderson's oeuvre, the *mise-en-abyme*, and its various manifestations. One might call this kind of representation - highly idiosyncratic of Anderson's style - a meta-sign of the enunciation, where many of the recognizable visual trademarks are just different expressions or variations. Said central strategy is, on the one hand, intrinsically related to the collector's aesthetics that pervade Anderson's filmography as Donna Kornhaber (2017) defends in her monograph. On the other hand, *mise-en-abyme* constructs the narrative of the film according to a *matryoshka-like* approach, i.e., over several juxtaposed or nested layers of meaning, by means of a metadiscursive and reflective use of the medium³.

In order to reveal this reflective quality operating at the very core of the *mise-en-abyme*, as well as its cinematic and audience implications, it is meaningful to start with one of the most immediate features of Wes Anderson's cinema: symmetry⁴. Thus, the images of a very high percentage of Andersonian shots are reflections of themselves with respect to a central vertical plane, which works as a mirror, and is projected in the frame as a usually implicit axis of symmetry. Apart from providing clues about a peculiar geometric conception of cinematic space, symmetry refers to pure optical reflexivity, to the self-referentiality of images with respect to themselves. The symmetry in Wes Anderson, however, would be almost anecdotal if it were not embedded in a broader concept of reflexivity, which affects his cinema at all levels, referring to the fundamental resources of the seventh art. Certainly, cinema itself is an immense set of mirrors, as Metz affirms in his article *The Imaginary Signifier* (Metz, 1975, pp. 52-53):

[T]he role of monocular perspective (hence of the camera) ... inscribes an empty emplacement for the spectator-subject, an all-powerful position which is that of God himself ... And it is true that as he identifies with himself as look, the spectator can do no other than identify with the camera, too, which has looked before him at what he is now looking at ... When I say that 'I see' the film, I mean thereby a unique mixture of two contrary currents: the film is what I receive, and it is also what I release, since it does not pre-exist my entering the auditorium and I only need close my eyes to suppress it. Releasing it, I am the projector, receiving it, I am the screen; in both these figures together, I am the camera, pointed yet recording.

Thus the constitution of the signifier in the cinema depends on a series of mirror-effects organized in a chain, and not on a single reduplication.

Few filmmakers seem as aware of this reflective condition in cinema as Anderson, who enjoys, in a recurrent and systematic way, making the mirror game visible, using it in quite uncommon ways, thus disturbing the viewer, who gets uncomfortable on leaving the role of a half-awake dreamer attributed to him by classic cinema. Anderson usually resorts to this type of maneuvering in an underhanded way, explicit enough for the viewer to be aware of the signs of the enunciation but preserving its illusionistic quality. To get to the bottom of this metaphor, it could be said that, in general, the viewer sees the hands of Anderson the magician – i.e., the tracks of Anderson the enunciator - in their resort to the reflexivity inherent to the medium itself. However, in a moment of the film that represents - until now - the climax of the scopic drive of his filmography, *Isle of Dogs* (2018) the illusionist exposes himself. The image of Tracy Walker (Picture 1), including four different metadiscursive levels, is an apex within Andersonianism that, however, gives access to his sanctuary, shamelessly uncovering one of its fundamental mechanisms, the conjurer's trick concealed underneath, the *mise-en-abyme*.

Picture 1: A shot of Tracy Walker as a paradigmatic example of *mise-en-abyme*.

Certainly, the *ad infinitum* reflection of Tracy and her companions is possible because the image literally takes Metz's text quoted above. The lens reflects what is projected. The viewer, who assimilates his perspective to that of a camera - which functions as a mirror - explicitly turns into, in this case, camera and screen, and the abysmal game of mirrors -which, in fact, is not a single duplicity, but an infinite multiplicity- becomes visible. Accordingly, the camera and the viewer, both literally used as the mirror, are included in the diegetic frontier⁵. There is no doubt that the image in Picture 1 falls within the definition of *mise-en-abyme* proposed by Stam *et al.* (1992, p. 205) within the epigraph of their book that refers to the "nature of reflexivity":

MISE-EN-ABYME, refers to the infinite regress of mirror reflections to denote the literary, painterly or filmic process by which a passage, a section or a sequence plays out in miniature the processes of the text as a whole.

The concept of *mise-en-abyme* is coined by the writer André Gide (2012, p. 49), who developed it from a type of heraldic representation, as he explains in an entry in his diary from 1893:

I rather like that in a work of art the theme of the work itself is thus transposed to the scale of the characters. Nothing enhances it better or establishes more clearly the proportions of the whole. Thus in the paintings by Memling or Quentin Metzys, a small dark convex mirror reflects, in turn, the interior of the room where the painted scene takes place. Something similar (albeit with slight differences) takes place in Velázquez's *Las Meninas*. Finally, in literature, there is the dumbshow scene in *Hamlet*; and in many other plays ... None of these examples is completely accurate. What would be much more so, and would better express what I was looking for in my *Cahiers*, in my *Narcisse* and in *La Tentative*, is the comparison with a coat of arms where a second one is placed in "abyeme" in the first one.

As can be seen, Gide refers both to the story within the story (the comedy scene in *Hamlet*) and to the image within the image (the mirrors present in both *Las Meninas* and the paintings by Memling or Metzys). The concept is interpreted differently by different authors although, among the multiple definitions, one proposed by the Spanish scholar Francisco Javier Gómez Tarín (2013, p. 52n5) adapts itself faithfully to Gide's text and is particularly useful to the purpose of this paper:

We understand by *mise en abîmé* the inclusion of a representation within the representation, as is the case of a film, or a play, or a television program, within the film. Through it, a metadiscursive use of the representation itself is carried out; hence the mirrors generate this type of matryoshka-like relationship, as it would also occur with frames, windows, reflective objects and, at the utmost, silhouettes or shadows...

The above quote establishes an immediate relationship with what Casetti and Di Chio call emblems of the emission. By its very nature, the concept of *mise-en-abyeme* is associated with the notion of reflexivity in Berthold Brecht, to whose epic theater the concept of Counter-Cinema defined by Peter Wollen is also indebted (see Stam *et al.*, 1992, p. 202). In fact, Anderson's *mise-en-abyeme* usually fulfills some of the characteristics of the Counter-Cinema, such as narrative intransitivity (i.e., the flow of the story is interrupted), estrangement (e.g., through direct interpellation), multiple diegesis or foregrounding (insofar as the discursive mechanism is made explicit).

Already *Rushmore* (1998), arguably the Rosetta Stone of *Andersonianism*, is conceived as a huge *mise-en-abyeme*: a constant theatrical representation - at several metadiscursive levels - within the filmic representation. When paying attention to the complete definition of Gómez Tarín, however, many other uses of this resource in this film are revealed such as (and only to mention some of particular relevance): 1) The *Making Time* montage sequence, describing all the extracurricular activities Max Fischer presides or has founded; 2) the composition of the shot when we first see Bert Fischer, based on a complex use of mirrors; 3) the long tracking shot where Max and Rosemary feed the fish and talk about their dead relatives, the first Anderson shot where a dollhouse aesthetic is recognizable; 4) the Cousteau-like documentary within the film and, 5) the first shot of the intermission of *Heaven & Hell*, where the lens of the camera is positioned at the mirror location.

As a result of this brief analysis, the wide scope and core relevance that the different modes of representations within representations have in Anderson's cinema can be intuited. Let us take a look at each one.

Strategies associated with theatricality

As we said before, there are several metadiscursive levels associated with this modality of *mise-en-abyme* in *Rushmore*, the first of which - the film itself is structured as a play - will be discussed further below.

The second level corresponds to the *representations of theatrical plays* in the film, present in *Rushmore*, *Moonrise Kingdom* (2012) and *Isle of Dogs*⁷. Common to all of them is the presence of religious elements: the catholic clothing and signs in *Rushmore*, the two fragments of the biblical *Noyes' Fludde*, by Benjamin Britten, in *Moonrise Kingdom*, and the funeral play to honor the alleged death of Atari in the case of *Isle of Dogs*.

A third metadiscursive level associated with theatricality refers to the *acting that the characters make of themselves*, and which is often associated with narcissistic or histrionic personality disorders. Sometimes this representation can be corrected and constitutes the fundamental transformation of the hero, as in the case of Max, Royal or Zissou; in other cases, such as that of M. Gustave, it is an existential and "incurable" performance.

The fourth strategy in this group corresponds to the *explicit calls to the viewer*, in the style of theatrical "asides", implying the extradiegetic presence of the audience, such as Max's sidelong glance after his *Serpico* play, or Rex looking at the camera in *Isle of Dogs*, while speaking directly to the audience, without the presence of a character off-camera as representative of the implicit viewer. Similarly, Suzy looks directly at the camera after the prologue and in the final shot of *Moonrise Kingdom*, the two milestones between which her love story with Sam takes place, and two direct calls requesting the empathy of the audience. A very particular, specially metaleptic case of this sort of strategy occurs in *The Darjeeling Limited* when Francis Whitman, directly looking at camera, says "We're invited to the funeral"; in doing so, not only does he address his brothers as figures of the implicit viewer, but at the same time he invites them *and* the implicit viewer to witness the ritual. Some intradiegetic narrators (such as the Author or Jupiter), and particularly those located in the diegetic frontier (such as Zissou or Bob Balaban), often resort to the above.

A fifth way of using theatricality is the *contrived use of lighting*, such as the artificial glow of Felicity Fox and Mr. Fox, the moment the restaurant lights dim when Zero Moustafa begins to tell Agatha's story, or the darkening of the sky when Chief explains the discovery of his canine aggressiveness.

The last type of recourse in this group would be determined by the *characters' conscious or unconscious staging*. On a conscious level, one can mention the representation that Max makes in Miss Cross' room, or that of Royal's own illness in the house on Archer Avenue. In a broad sense, Sam's and Suzy's dance is also a moment in which both characters are the conscious authors of some kind of ritual staging. At the unconscious level, there would be the shots as *tableaux vivant* that assume the presence of a stage, but are not explicit theatrical representations per se, and almost always located on a metadiegetic level different from the main diegesis. An obvious example is Petey's song in *Fantastic Mr. Fox*: it is clear that the animals are not on a stage, but the way in which the farms are conceived within the image, as well as the choreography, immediately refers to a scenic representation.

Obviously, the combination of several of these strategies within a single shot is possible. The *Making Time* sequence in *Rushmore*, a real milestone in Anderson's filmography, is a good example of this.

Texts that work as a framework

This category is associated with the cinematic narrator. The concept refers to the fact that certain elements recurrently present throughout the film - and usually from its very beginning - request that the implicit viewer reads it as another type of text: a play (*Rushmore*), a book⁸ (*The Royal Tenenbaums* (2001), *Fantastic Mr. Fox* (2009), *Moonrise Kingdom*⁹, *The Grand Budapest Hotel* (2014)) and a documentary by Steve Zissou - or its making of - in the case of *The Life Aquatic with Steve Zissou* (2004). *The Darjeeling Limited* (2007) is a particular case, since the framework in that case is not a text, but a train journey. Only *Bottle Rocket* (1996) and *Isle of Dogs* - although it is divided in chapters - can be excluded from this group.

Interestingly enough, all above mentioned cases except *The Darjeeling Limited* refer either to the work of a film director or, most frequently, to the work of a writer. This can be considered as an expression of Anderson's primitive vocation, that of a writer, as he himself declared in several interviews (i.e., Seitz, 2013, p. 41). Not only has he not denied this first inclination, but he has rather cultivated it further through his films, becoming one of the clearest cases of contemporary author-writer, according to the *cabieristic* approach of this term. Equally, his career as a filmmaker is tightly related to books: firstly because he discovered movies by reading books on cinema; secondly, because he shares this passion for books with his essential cinematic father figure, François Truffaut¹⁰, as he explains in an interesting interview with Paul Holdengräber (2014, 27' 30").

Texts within the text

This category, the broadest one, refers directly to the image within the image that Gide cites in reference to the *Las Meninas* mirror, and partially overlaps with what Casetti and Di Chio call emblems of the emission. These are images within the image; generally speaking books, movies, paintings, televisions or screens. Following Gómez Tarín, the various types of frames (windows, etc.) that reframe the characters could even be included here. Within this category, the texts that invoke a different metadiegetic level stand out, such as *the book-like montage sequences*, among which it is worth highlighting the well-known *Making Time* montage sequence in *Rushmore* or *Judy is a Punk* in *The Royal Tenenbaums*. The latter representing the report of a detective - the figure of a narratee that flows into that of a narrator¹¹ - about Margot's affairs. Both fragments are conceived as a succession of *tableaux vivants*, in which each shot represents one of Max's activities or episodes from Margot's double life -made explicit through the supertitles- such as a visual book as a metonym for the physical yearbook or report, i.e., displaying their respective contents. Plus, in the first case, Max visually interpellates the viewer in many of the *tableaux*, implying, as has been seen, another metadiscursive level. In the second case there are several orders of *mise-en-abyme* in some of the shots. Especially evident is that of the *Rive Gauche*, in which Margot closes the window until it mirrors the Eiffel Tower.

Regarding the *films within the film*, apart from the special case of *The Life Aquatic*, representing a constant exercise of metacinema, some quasi-documentary segments could be mentioned, such as the shots in which Bob Balaban defines the geography of New Penzance or the impressive moments of the sushi preparation or the kidney transplant - both shot overhead - in *Isle of Dogs*.

Besides, *screens* represent an important kind of text within the movie. Screens can appear alone; if so, the limits of the screen height approximately coincide with those of the frame, or together with other active elements of the shot, a resource that often repeats itself in *Isle of Dogs*. The screens can give additional information about the shot, or they can repeat what is shown or reveal what is implicit. Within this category, an additional depth level is presented, provided by either the *multiplicity of screens* in the same shot, first appearing in *The Life Aquatic*, or the *split screen* itself, which Anderson uses in *Moonrise Kingdom* and *Isle of Dogs*. A particular case, although inanimate, would be the *paintings or photographs* insofar as they suppose a story within the story, such as the insert in *Rushmore* showing the affair between Miss Cross and Herman Blume. A more interesting case is the Japanese mural on which Jupiter narrates the story of the *Isle of Dogs* at the beginning of the film; Felicity's pictures of storms can also be included here, expressing her state of inner anxiety about being married to Mr. Fox.

Following Gómez Tarín's notion, the abundant and diverse *reframes* can be cited here, such as frames, holes or windows¹² - such as the portholes of the *Deep Search* -, binoculars - especially Suzy Bishop's, among many others -, or the use of the *iris* starting from *Fantastic Mr. Fox*. A particularly original case would be the *mental projections* of the characters, present in both animated films, where Mr. Fox's olfactory perception or Chief's imagination become visible.

Finally, there would be *other types of documents* of a very diverse nature, such as the frequent letters that constitute a privileged mode of communication in Anderson's films, maps, cards, etc.

The mirror games

As explained above, both the cinema and the *mise-en-abyme* are based on a set of complex mirror reflections. Thus, mirror games are themselves a privileged category, leading in Wes Anderson's works to truly astonishing exercises in reflexivity. On the one hand, there are the somewhat complex, but relatively common *games of specular reflections* within the frame, as in the appearance of Bert Fischer in *Rushmore*, or when Major Kobayashi decides to donate one kidney to his nephew in *Isle of Dogs*.

An even more interesting case within this category is the use of the *camera lens as a mirror*, first used in the mentioned moment of the intermission of *Heaven & Hell* in *Rushmore*, merging the regimes of emission and reception, narrator and narratee, concurrently originating in the spectator the estrangement typical when the character looks directly at the camera and a peculiar identification with the characters that are on the screen. This type of strategy - which can be confused with the simple interpellations to the viewer described above, but which is of a radically different nature - is used in two key anthological moments of *The Royal Tenenbaums*: in the much-commented *Cast of Characters*

sequence, and in the montage *Needle in the Hay*, in which Richie's suicide attempt is narrated. For the sake of simplicity, we will start with the second, synthesized in the four shots of Picture 2. The first two (a, b) show the beginning and an intermediate point of Richie Tenenbaum's metamorphosis - conceived as a ritual of detachment - after discovering Margot's love affairs. Shot (b) is especially significant as Richie removes the sunglasses that he has worn during his adult life. Glasses are an emblem of reception, according to Casetti and Di Chio (1994, p. 229). By removing them, however, Richie is open to true identification with the implicit viewer, as he allows it with himself: the glasses were the symbol of a life that is too harsh, of a reality so disconcerting that it could only be seen through a protector filter, also acting as an agent of identity distortion. The viewer discovers his terribly sad look at the exact same time Richie does: more than the glasses themselves, it is their absence that becomes an emblem of the reception. The dramatic effect is huge and acts as preparation for one of the hardest moments in Anderson's filmography. The immediately following shot (c) explicitly shows what the viewer already knew: that the camera lens occupies the place of the mirror during the rest of the sequence. Finally, in (d) Richie speaks directly to the spectator, and to himself, with a self-destructive phrase: *I'm going to kill myself tomorrow*. The words - and their deadpan manifestation - reinforce both the distancing and the identification in the viewer: it is difficult to remain impassive in the face of Richie's confession, in his abrupt descent into hell. The Tenenbaum sees his sadness reflected in the viewer. The application of the Lacanian mirror theory to the cinema, according to Metz, implies that the spectator (unlike the child, in his fantasy of narcissistic omnipotence) is outside the mirror, although he can identify with everything he sees in it (Metz, 1975, pp. 50-52). By positioning the camera lens - identified with the viewer's point of view - as the mirror, Anderson achieves the almost impossible, the ideal of metalepsis: to include the viewer, to say the least, on the frontier of the diegesis, since the *mise-en-abyme* in this case does not occur within the diegesis, not even within two different diegetic levels, but between the interior and the exterior of the diegesis. In other words, the viewer is Richie's mirror, but not only identifying at the camera level, but more so as the secondary cinematic identification with Richie is reinforced, since the identification postulate is made literal in a psychoanalytic sense: "*Identification* = «I see as you see, from your *positions*»" (Stam et al., 1992, p. 153).

Picture 2: Four shots of the montage Needle in the Hay that reveal a metaleptical use of the camera lens as a mirror.

Somewhat more complex is the *Cast of Characters* sequence, which is a categorical, non-narrative fragment, like *Making Time* or - at least partially - *Judy is a Punk*: a sort of collection of the various characters, and, ultimately, of varied attitudes towards life that highlight a deep pessimism about human nature, an ugly face that, as in the metonymic case of Royal, wants to be hidden by means of a mask. They all prepare themselves - putting on makeup, shaving, grooming - to go on stage, to start the performance. Moreover, all of them *are* representation, the fiction of what one is not, the reflection of what one would like to be. Self-reflection on this fictional character is marked by a new look towards the diegetic frontier in which these shots are found, made explicit by the supertitle presenting each actor and his character. An awareness of one's own ignominy, which leads, as it does Richie, to wanting to hide, even behind a camera, symbolizing one's own *mise-en-abyme*. But here the mirror is even crueler than in the case of Richie's suicide. In some way, the characters are reflected in the viewer they are looking at, whose presence they assume. And here at least some of his most unspeakable fears, of his most humiliating ridiculousness, are on the screen, under the vicarious presence of the Tenenbaum family. On the other hand, the two sequences reveal the beginning and the end of a representation, adding to both a higher order of *mise-en-abyme*, that increases within each image: Royal's mask, the double repetition Chas' actions on Ari and Uzi, the mirror behind Eli, and Luke's camera, as well as the repetition of the words *Côte D'Ivoire* and the mirror to his left are elements of *mise-en-abyme* within the *mise-en-abyme*.

Two extreme cases of the mirror games would be the *symmetry* mentioned at the beginning of the article, in which one half of the image is a specular reflection of the other, or the *Doppelgänger*, the character that unfolds, prefigured for the first time in Chas' twin sons, Ari and Uzi, and more interestingly developed in *Isle of Dogs* with Spots and Chief¹³. Once again, this resource drinks from the essence of cinema while challenging it. According to Metz (1975, pp. 47-48), any object in cinema "will not be there when the spectators see it ... it will have delegated its reflection to them ... [T]he perceived is not really the object, it is its shade, its phantom, its double, its *replica* in a new kind of mirror". In this sense, Chief is Spots' real double - within the imaginary domain of the diegesis - the

materialization of his ghost, to the extent that Atari goes looking for the second and ends up being accompanied by the first.

The Cornell boxes

A fifth strategy of *mise-en-abyme* is what some scholars, based on the article by Michael Chabon (2013), relate to Joseph Cornell's boxes. The fame of the artist, poet and experimental filmmaker is mainly due to his boxes, created from found objects and juxtaposed in an irrational way¹⁴ - thus being assimilated to surrealism - that reproduced non-existent, imaginary worlds full of nostalgia. The assimilation between Cornell and Anderson has to do both with the tone of the work and with the tendency to confine spaces, to create worlds within worlds. For both, as Chabon points out, the box itself matters more than the content of the box, the discourse more than the story. This trend is associated to various manifestations. The most evident is the *dollhouse aesthetic*, which permeates his work from the aforementioned tracking shot where Max and Rosemary feed the fish, and is repeated whenever the camera travels through the cross section of a building or vehicle, as if passing from one box to another. A direct reference is given in *The Royal Tenenbaums*, following one of Margot's dioramas, of a marked autobiographical character (Seitz, 2013, p. 146). A privileged exponent of this type of aesthetic is the *Belafonte* in *The Life Aquatic*, conceived as a Cornell box with many boxes inside. Another paradigmatic example is the long tracking shot of *The Darjeeling Limited*, which is like the epitome of Anderson's ability to represent a small story built in each shot as if it were a box, and the constructivist character of his cinema: train compartments that actually harbor other stories, disguised as other realities, such as an airplane cabin or a hotel room. It is, on the other hand, the maximum expression of a non-place¹⁵ (a train) turned into a place - like the burrows of *Fantastic Mr. Fox* and unlike the Bishop house in *Moonrise Kingdom* - two other paradigmatic examples of the dollhouse aesthetics. A special use of this *mise-en-abyme* as Cornell's boxes takes place in *Isle of Dogs*, in which Anderson shows not only what happens in a compartment, but at the limit of the scopic drive, what is inside the characters themselves, exhibiting a *cross section of the body*, as if it were an X-ray study. The character is no longer assimilated to a space: the character *is* the space, the box. Certainly, the characteristic of Cornell boxes is not reduced to the aesthetics of a dollhouse or, in other words, the box does not exist solely when its cross section is explicit, but also in those shots that seem to enjoy the *characters' confinement*. Thus, besides the obvious examples already discussed above, Chabon (2013) cites the dressing room where Sam and Suzy first meet in *Moonrise Kingdom* as an example of a Cornell box. There are no partition sections here, no windows: just doll-like characters, looking at the child who is playing with them (Anderson) and the friends he has invited to play (the spectators). There are countless examples - e.g. the frequent shots inside elevators, one of Anderson's favorite non-places - all of them a clear sign of the enunciation.

In-depth editing

Another strategy of *mise-en-abyme*, present from *Bottle Rocket* on, is one in which, within the main action, space is left for a secondary action that has nothing to do with the first, but is quite disturbing as it is out of place and generates a contrast between stasis and movement. Sometimes the action "within the action" is highlighted by reframing; for

example, the first time this technique is used, Anthony talks to Inez after their first sexual encounter, but the romantic scene is disturbed by Dignan's fight inside the bar. The same can be said about the recurrent cameos of a small boy named Ryan - the one who swims around Herman Blume - in *Rushmore*. Other examples are when the boy jumps on a trampoline as Sam and Suzy get engaged, the killer whale pirouetting during the distressed interview between Steve Zissou and Janet Winslett-Richardson, or the group of sailors that parade in the background as Richie watches Margot get off the bus. It is quite clear that in all of the above cases the contrast between the main actions or words - which are taken very seriously and/or emotionally by the characters involved in them - and the inappropriate absurdity of the actions in the background or next to the main one is yet another expression of the deadpan humor that sustains the Andersonian comedy.

Nested film techniques

At times, Anderson decides to invoke one universe within another, through the simultaneous use on the frame or sequentially, of *different filmic techniques*. First glimpses are obtained through the use of stop-motion in *The Life Aquatic* or the drawing of a diagram in traditional animation when explaining the game of whackbat in *Fantastic Mr. Fox*. The stop-motion animations on the *Moonrise Kingdom* maps or the animated models of the elevator that goes up to *The Grand Budapest Hotel* would be further examples. Once again, the most obsessive use is found in *Isle of Dogs*, in which stop-motion animation is usually mixed with traditional animation that generally appears on televisions or screens, or as flashbacks. As they belong to the technological order of filmic discourse, *frame ratio changes* can also be mentioned here, whether fictitious or real, as will be seen below in the case of *The Grand Hotel Budapest*. Lastly, there is the use of *black and white*, both within a color shot or sequentially. The first case is mainly seen in *Isle of Dogs*, where black and white television programs appear in otherwise colored frames. The most prominent example of sequential - and narratively significant - use of black and white happens in the closing sequence of the metadiegetic level of 1932 in *The Grand Budapest Hotel*, where it becomes a symbol of the tragic end of M. Gustave and of the dark shadows spreading over Europe¹⁶.

The silhouettes

Following Gómez Tarín, an extreme case of *mise-en-abyme* would consist in the use of silhouettes. This happens clearly for the first time in *Moonrise Kingdom*, in the sequence where Sam and Suzy are rescued by Captain Shark¹⁷ and reappears in an especially striking way in the *Isle of Dogs*. This technique is a reminder of the origins of cinema: it is an exceptional new utilization by Anderson of techniques that were used in the early days and are now considered obsolete. They are reminiscent of Lotte Reininger's silhouette films and the use of shadows in German Expressionism.

The story within the story

Gide's mention of the comedy scene in *Hamlet*, is an example of metadiegesis, which is the most basic and universal case of what is usually understood as *mise-en-abyme*. In his obsession to make discourse visible, Anderson's metadiegesis are often metadiscursive. The extreme case is found in the *The Grand Budapest Hotel*, in which a particular aesthetic underlies each of the stories, also marked by a different frame ratio, according to what was

usual in the cinema of each reproduced era. Obviously, flashbacks in general belong to this category, as well as categorical sequences out of time, such as the aforementioned *Making Time* or *Judy is a Punk*, or the succession of *tableaux* showing Etheline Tenenbaum's suitors.

Self-referential biographical elements

As explained, the reflexivity of *mise-en-abyme* can be especially related to Lacan's mirror phase, a phase characterized by the child's narcissism. A particular case of *mise-en-abyme* is brought about by the *autobiographical allusions* that, as the interviews with the author underline, are abundant in the Andersonian filmography. One example could be the glasses that Etheline uses in *The Royal Tenenbaums*, which belonged to Anderson's mother, who was an archaeologist like the matriarch of the Tenenbaum clan (see Collin, 2014). A privileged expression of these self-referential, narcissistic elements pertains to characters that are authors, especially Steve Zissou.

Putting it all together

We briefly mentioned that the combinations between different strategies can generate a higher order of *mise-en-abyme*. A particularly eloquent example is shown in Picture 3, which constitutes a seventh-order abyss setting. The image belongs to a film that can be seen as another means, a book (1); there is another text (a picture) within the frame (2); Zero appears on the scene reflected in a circular mirror (3); M. Gustave dramatizes the pose of the *Boy with apple* (4); everything takes place in a train compartment which, in a way, becomes partly museum (5); and the 4:3 frame (6) reveals that it is a story within another story (7).

Picture 3: Higher order *mise-en-abyme* in a shot of *The Grand Budapest Hotel*.

Conclusion

Wes Anderson can be considered as a renovator of auteurism, who offers something new to the author question. Beyond the self-conscious construction of his authorial image, mainly through the paratexts that accompany the Criterion editions of his

movies, Wes Anderson's cinema is packed with reflexive, metadiscursive signs of the enunciation that reveal his presence. Some of the most recognizable visual signs of the enunciation are manifestations of a central narrative strategy, the *mise-en-abyme*, which affects the very core of his particular style of filmmaking. These strategies range from the very concept of symmetry immediately recognizable as a typical characteristic in the majority of his frames, to the complex metaleptical use of the lens of the camera as a mirror, aiming to include the viewer into the diegetic frontier, thus transgressing and surpassing the usual categories of the intradiegetic and extradiegetic, in a game with the basics of cinema itself. Other manifestations of the *mise-en-abyme* include the recurrent Andersonian dollhouse shots, the nested cinematic techniques, different kinds of texts within the text or stories within the story and, in general, several expressions of ubiquitous matryoshka-like aesthetics. Moreover, the concept of *mise-en-abyme* itself is based on the reflection, the repetition and the multiplicity of elements and techniques, and so it can be considered a key aspect of Anderson's cinema - a collector's cinema - linked to the characteristic saturation of his films. However, contrary to what is often asserted, this saturation is not primarily visual, but rather, as Gooch (2007, p. 33) notes: "Anderson's well-known love of small details does not so much offer an excess of image beyond narrative but rather an excess of narrative beyond image." An excess that occurs in a privileged way through the constant nesting of narratives that involves the *mise-en-abyme*.

¹ Due to the economy of language, we refer to all genders by using the masculine.

² This *dependency* on his fans, as well as the dependency on his collaborators or *cinematic family* is a contradiction of the principles of the author theory, as it defended that the writer-director is the only author of the film. As (Orgeron, 2007, p. 59) notes: "Anderson ... has participated in a method of self-representation that makes his *dependence* on others a proud thing, the defining feature of his particular brand of authorship. In other words, the reborn author as exemplified by Anderson *appears* more prominent than ever; but his centrality ... remains *in spite* of attempts to document the many collaborative layers of the filmmaking enterprise."

³ See also the article by Kim Wilkins (2018), who refers, albeit only indirectly, to the *mise-en-abyme* dominating Anderson's "assembled worlds". She also points out to the "juxtaposition", "reflexivity" and "overtly artifices" (ibid. pp. 153 and 156) of the Andersonian narratives, as well as to the collector's aesthetic as defined by Kornhaber (2017), which finds a privileged expression in Cornell's boxes. Wilkin's article further analyzes Anderson's nested worlds from the perspective of the New Sincerity and the intertextuality, thus offering a complementary approach to the present contribution, as it explains why the artificiality generated by the *mise-en-abyme* can "mediate the intensity of negative emotions and psychological problems" (p. 154) that arguably pervade Anderson's thematic and ideological spaces.

⁴ Although this article is devoted to the *mise-en-abyme* as a particular case of *mise-en-scène*, thus essentially belonging to the visual realm, symmetry in Wes Anderson's cinema reaches far beyond the limits of the image. For example, the cyclic structure of narrative time (*Erzählzeit*) in *Bottle Rocket*, *The Darjeeling Limited*, *Moonrise Kingdom* and *The Grand Budapest Hotel*, divides the main diegesis into two narrative halves, separated from each other by a central segment of particular importance, such as the nested funerals in *The Darjeeling Limited*, Sam and Suzy's dance on the beach, or *The Society of Crossed Keys* montage in the case of metadiegetic level corresponding to 1932 in *The Grand Budapest Hotel*. In all of these movies, the final sequence is a variation of the initial one, and, arguably, the second half of the film rewrites the elements appearing in the first one. Of course, the case of *The Grand Budapest Hotel* is very special, since the symmetry is applicable to all four metadiegetic levels corresponding to the present, to 1985, 1968 and 1932. In the latter level, the diegesis is caught between both train sequences, excluding the sort of prologue that introduces the main characters. The symmetry in the case of *The Grand Budapest Hotel* is also particularly interesting because it extends up to the soundtrack. As Motazedian (2016) explains, the tonal design in this movie is so conceived that "in a beautiful instance of tonal symmetry, the chronological order in which the [musical] keys *enter* the film sound track is palindromic with the order in which they *exit*" (p. 105, see also Figure 4.8) so that music reinforces the mentioned structural symmetry of the movie. In fact, "[b]oth the narrative and the sound track build up to the climatic apex of [the key] of F Major" (p. 105) in which the music of *The Society of Crossed Keys* montage is composed.

⁵ We understand by diegetic frontier the ambiguous space that is established between two different metadiegetic levels, or between the inside and the outside of the diegesis. Wes Anderson often makes a transgressive - i.e., metaleptic - use of this space, where he likes to place some characters, the music and, at times, the implicit viewer. Thus, the diegetic frontier sometimes acts as point of tangency between the intradiegetic and the extradiegetic, especially in the latter case.

⁶ Gómez Tarín writes the expression *mise-en-abyme* itself slightly differently from Stam *et al.* The latter is more common and will be used hereinafter.

⁷ There are also two shots in *The Royal Tenenbaums* that show the ovation at the end of Margot Tenenbaum's first play as well as a parodic line of dialogue that refers to how Royal introduced her to other people as "his adopted daughter" when she was a child. We understand these two shots are different in their purposes from the ones in the other three movies cited, not only because they lack any religious references, but also because they do not contain a development of the theatrical representation. Rather, only a moment in time is captured and, in the first of the mentioned cases, it is not even a part of the representation.

⁸ Sloane (2018, p. 255) affirms that "in reality, all Wes Anderson's films are books interpreted and projected in the mind of a child reader". Aside from the fact that Anderson's films seem more twisted than a healthy child might imagine, the presumption of totality, as it turns out, is wrong.

⁹ The association of *Moonrise Kingdom* with a book is less evident than in the aforementioned cases. Nevertheless, many of the elements contained in Suzy's stolen books – such as adventures, orphans, or even the superpowers, in Suzy's case her binoculars – are of key importance in the film's argument. On the other hand, the director himself has explained that he conceived *Moonrise Kingdom* as one of Suzy's books (Anderson, 2015, 2' 08").

¹⁰ The cinematic relationship between Anderson and Truffaut has been approached by Orgeron (2007) in terms of the author theory in his seminal article. There are many other cases in which Anderson refers to the huge influence of Truffaut in his cinema, most prominently in Seitz (2013, p. 312), where Anderson acknowledges that he decided to become a filmmaker after having seen one of the founding films of the Nouvelle Vague, *The 400 blows* (*Les quatre cents coups*, François Truffaut, 1959). See also Lyman (2002) and Zahm and Le-Tan (2008).

¹¹ For a precise definition of all narratologic concepts used in this paper, such as narrator, narratee, etc., see Prince (1987).

¹² Window frames are especially recurrent in *The Royal Tenenbaums*. The presence of characters - essentially women - in window frames is one of the most recognizable visual elements of the melodrama (see Huerta Floriano, 2019, p. 136). This fact, along with many others - such as the use of music for expressing the character's feelings, as Piechota (2006) demonstrates - makes it possible to interpret this film and, by extension, a big portion of Anderson's works, in terms of comedy as the parodic reversal of melodrama.

¹³ The study of both couples - Ari and Uzi, Spots and Chief - and especially the latter, could lead to a very interesting analysis on the notions of role, person and actant.

¹⁴ Wes Anderson's only example of artistic production besides his movies or advertisements helps understand the primacy of aesthetic over logic in his particular way of juxtaposing objects. On the invitation of the director of the Kunsthistorisches Museum in Vienna, Sabine Haag, and the curator of the modern and contemporary art section of this institution, Jasper Sharp, Wes Anderson and his girlfriend Juman Maouf were the authors of the exhibition "*Spitzmaus Mummy in a Coffin and Other Treasures*", which ran between November 6, 2018 and April 28, 2019, showing a total of 430 articles freely chosen out of the 4.5 million objects gathered in the different sections and warehouses of the museum. Sharp explained how Wes and Juman had chosen the objects "not according to their antiqueness, origin, rareness or position in the historical-artistic canon" as it is usual among the art curators, but rather "according to their color, size, shape or material", juxtaposing some objects with others "that would never be exposed together in a museum" and thus "ignoring the complete value system that serves the museum as a reference" (Streiff Corti, 2019).

¹⁵ The notion of non-place, which seems to be relevant for the understanding of Anderson's cinema, was defined by the scholar Gérard Imbert (2017, p. 66) as follows: "Non-places are not 'territories' in the anthropological sense of the word - places that define identity -, but empty places of non-identity, in which the characters move and at times literally and metaphorically get lost. There is equivalence between wandering and existential wandering and it is translated physically. Even the landscape can have more physical existence than the body itself, but this refers to an invisible place, which can be that of fantasy."

¹⁶ In fact, the sequence where Sam and Suzy are rescued by Captain Shark could be considered as the first one where sequential black and white in Wes Anderson's filmography is used. However, in this particular case, it would be more precise to talk about a monochrome sequence with a dark blue predominant hue, at times broken by light traces of other colors. In any case, the overall effect and the narrative meaning associated to death resemble the use of black and white in the mentioned sequence of *The Grand Budapest Hotel*. In this latter case, however, the use of pure black and white can also be interpreted as a reference to the movies of the 30s that inspired the film.

¹⁷ Perhaps the moment of the fight between Mr. Fox and Rat could be considered as a previous use of silhouettes; when he is electrocuted, his skeleton appears as in an X-ray, which is reminiscent of a silhouette. However, the appeal seems to be more incidental than conscious and, in any case, ambiguous. A somewhat clearer case can be found in *Moonrise Kingdom* earlier than the one indicated, although less obvious, occurs when the khaki scouts run across a bridge.

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